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PIECES OF PAINTING IN AN ENGLISH LESSON AS A MEANS OF DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

ИЗАТОВА АЛЬМИРА БЕКЕТАЕВНА

Старший преподаватель кафедры филологии, УО «Alikhan Bokeikhan University»,
Семей, Казахстан

Аннотация: *Статья ставит своей целью исследовать особенности использования произведений живописи на уроке иностранного языка в качестве инструмента формирования у учащихся коммуникативной компетенции. В статье рассмотрены возможные задания, снабженные адекватно подобранными наглядными материалами в виде картин известных художников, при выполнении которых учащиеся отрабатывают лексику, грамматические конструкции, совершенствуют навыки говорения. В статье доказывается идея того, что на уроках с использованием произведений живописи учащиеся обучаются монологическому высказыванию-описанию, обогащают свой словарный запас лексикой, связанной с темой картины, расширяют горизонты в области искусства, развивают воображение и творческий потенциал. Идеи, заявленные в статье, позволяют сделать выводы, что вопрос применения произведений живописи при моделировании речевых ситуаций в процессе обучения иностранному языку достаточно перспективен для дальнейшего его изучения и применения в практической деятельности в школе.*

Ключевые слова: *живопись, коммуникативная компетенция, искусство, воображение, речь, творческое мышление*

Annotation. *This article aims to explore the use of paintings in foreign language lessons as a tool for developing learners' communicative competence. The article examines possible assignments, supported by appropriately selected visual aids in the form of paintings by famous artists, during which learners practice vocabulary, grammar constructions, and improve speaking skills. The article argues that lessons using paintings enable learners to develop descriptive statements, enrich their vocabulary with words related to the painting's theme, expand their horizons in the field of art, and develop their imagination and creativity. The ideas presented in the article suggest that the use of paintings to simulate speech situations in foreign language teaching holds considerable promise for further study and practical application in schools.*

Keywords: *painting, communicative competence, art, imagination, speech, creative thinking*

Nowadays, the primary goal of teaching a foreign language as a subject area is, to develop foreign language communicative competence, in other words, the ability to communicate in the target language. Furthermore, learning a foreign language is "one of the opportunities for developing a linguistically engaging individual, capable and willing to engage in intercultural communication" [1, p. 9]. The teacher's primary task is to cultivate individuals prepared to work in the multilingual and culturally diverse environment of modern society. To achieve this, teachers must develop critical thinking skills, instill universal human values, and foster skills for communicating and thinking in different languages, empathy, and a positive attitude toward cultural differences.

English language classes have enormous potential for developing aesthetic culture, enabling learners to explore the beauty of the world through the language, culture, and art of other countries and peoples.

Incorporating fragments of visual art, which can be used at different stages of the lesson and at different levels of subject-matter skill development, not only introduces something new and extends beyond the subject matter, but also provides a completely new perspective on global masterpieces from various artistic movements. This type of art is appropriate for use in English lessons in senior grades, where elements of critical analysis already form the basis of cognitive activity.

As a means of pictorial clarity, works of art perform tasks of various kinds, the most important of which are "semanticizing, accompanying, communicative, and acculturating" [2, p. 127]. In accordance with these functions, A.I. Yakimovich identifies the following areas in working with works of art in a foreign language lesson:

«1) the use of pictures as illustrations, creating a "national background" for teaching, providing a "country-specific setting" for learners;
2) the use of pictures as a means of visualization for the semantization of vocabulary;
3) the use of pictures in work on developing learners' monologue and dialogic speech» [2, p. 127].

In foreign language lessons in senior grades, paintings can be considered, among other things, as a means of developing learners' communicative competence and verbal and intellectual activity. As L. A. Khodyakova asserts: "Working with a painting provides students with extralinguistic knowledge about the world around them, facilitates the use of thematically related words, contributes to the enrichment of students' vocabulary with various kinds of emotional-evaluative words, and develops situational speech" [3, p. 20]. Painting, as an extralinguistic material, not only reflects the surrounding world but also conveys specific information about events, places, people, historical and social phenomena. An artist, like a writer, communicates their philosophical and spiritual vision of the world, their attitude toward it, through imaginary images.

Paintings have the greatest potential for developing learners' creative thinking, while also fostering and nurturing active, creative foreign-language speech.

The use of paintings in foreign language lessons offers a number of didactic advantages:

- «- they ensure repeated repetition of certain structures, if their repetition is intended;
- speech tasks are solved: one speaks, the others listen;
- natural situations for communication emerge" [4, p. 29].

The use of paintings in English lessons promotes the development of the ability to plan one's speech based on a specific communicative task and the ability to express one's point of view in accordance with a specific task.

For example, the task "Describe a room" is a classic task for practicing the construction *there is/there are*, prepositions of place, articles, and vocabulary related to the topic "House. Flat." In this case, it would be appropriate to use paintings of artists' rooms to describe and offer the following task:

- Look at the room in Ivan Shishkin's painting "Before the Mirror." Try to guess the period (19th century, 20th century, etc.). Use "there is"/"there are" to describe the room's interior.

When practicing vocabulary on the topic "Food" and reinforcing the pronouns *some/any/much/many/no*, it is advisable to use still life and offer the following task:

- Take a look at the «Still Life with a Crystal Glass» by Yulia Kravchenko and describe what you see. Use these structures: "There's some + uncountable noun. There are some + countable noun. There isn't any + countable/uncountable noun. There is no + countable/uncountable noun. There are many/much + noun (countable/uncountable)".

It is recommended to practice the construction «used to» using pictures depicting past realities that were commonplace but are no longer so, for example:

- Have a look at Giovanni Vepkhvadze's painting "Still Life with Old Books". The painting depicts various household items, for instance, a magnifying glass, a kerosene lamp, an inkwell, a pocket watch, and a photograph frame from the 19th century and conveys the vibe of a bygone era. Tell what people in the past could do with the objects pictured. Use «used to/didn't use to + verb».

To practice the *Present Continuous*, the teacher can choose any image with a clear, obvious action and ask the learner to describe it using the *Present Continuous*, after explaining that the action in the picture is happening now. A recommended painting for this purpose can serve Georges-Pierre Seurat's "A Sunday Afternoon on the Island of La Grande Jatte."

To describe bygone days, it would be appropriate to use pictures that reflect some historical events, and in this case, it is important to select those illustrations that are easy enough to describe, for example:

- Using the *Past Simple* and *Past Continuous*, describe what happened/was happening in 1789 according to Eugène Delacroix's painting "Liberty Leading the People." Think and tell what might have happened before the events depicted in the painting.

When reinforcing the *Present Simple*, it's methodically useful to use a painting depicting a person and their daily life. A portrait of a person and their surroundings can reveal a lot about their life, for example:

- Look at the lady in Édouard Monet's painting "Bar at Forly-Bergère." Who do you think she is? What does she do for a living? Try describing her typical workday using the *Present Simple*. How does she feel? What does she see every day in this bar?

In senior grades, it's methodologically appropriate to use paintings in foreign language lessons directly to develop verbal and cognitive activity on the topic of "Art," where the objectives include teaching monologues such as "descriptions"; developing a broad understanding of art; and instilling a taste for painting.

Working with paintings typically follows a specific sequence. Learners are first presented with an educational text about the artist, their works, and the history of their creation. This is followed by direct activity, including demonstrations of the works, followed by discussion, such as:

- Imagine that you are a guide and describe the place depicted in the painting.

Before completing the task, it is advisable to prepare handouts with set phrases and expressions:

"In the center/ middle we can see a ..."; "In the foreground there is a ..."; "In the background there are ..."; "It is situated in ..."; "...stands on the left/ right"; "In the distance we can make out the outline of a ..."; "At first glance, ..."; "But if you look closely, you can see ..."; "It looks like ..."; "I can hardly make out (= see)"

- Imagine you're an art critic. Describe your feelings and ideas as you watch the picture «Girl with a Pearl Earring» by Johannes Vermeer.

The learner is free to describe the emotions and feelings the painting evokes. Again, the teacher is recommended to provide their own example as a model:

«In this painting, we see a beautiful and enigmatic girl, captured by the equally enigmatic Dutch artist Johannes Vermeer. For over three centuries, this girl has captivated gazes, drawn to her bottomless eyes, youthful oval face, unusual headdress, and earring. The image is inspired by the artist's love, and we, the viewers, feel it vividly. The girl's eyes radiate openness and kindness. This work by Johannes Vermeer can be called a hymn to youth, a youth just entering its prime, so timid and unaware of its future beauty and strength. One can gaze at the painting endlessly, inventing and reinterpreting its life story, making all sorts of guesses, and still walk away from it with a special feeling, a sense of its mystery unsolved».

While working with painting, learners enrich their vocabulary with words related to the theme of the painting, art history terms, and expand their horizons in the field of art: they learn about artists, types of painting, the eras depicted, etc.

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